

THE ROLE OF ACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS TO THINK CREATIVELY

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Abstract. This article shows the effectiveness of using active methods of teaching in directing primary school pupils to creative thinking, touched on the possibilities of using "Creative text based on a picture", "Fifth, sixth, seventh...is extra", "Chainword" " during lessons.

Keywords: primary education, creative thinking, "Creative text based on a picture", "Fifth, sixth, seventh...is extra", "Chainword", creative work.

On the basis of the order of the Minister of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 372 dated December 5, 2022 "On the further improvement of continuous methodological services in the public education system", one of the important factors in the development of methods promotion is to direct students to "Creative thinking" (to reach for innovations in order to achieve their goals, to make unusual decisions, to teach inventive skills).

The following main conclusions should be taken into account when directing to creative thinking:

- a pupil must learn, think, invent on his own, otherwise no one can teach him anything;
- the teacher organizes a process that helps pupils to "discover" knowledge;
- knowledge is not a copy copied from existence, implementing it in the direction of understanding human formation is an important situation.

Tasks, games, and interactive methods that encourage pupils to be active motivate pupils to think creatively, actively solve the received information, express their opinions freely, take the initiative, find solutions to problems in groups, work collaboratively, and express their opinions in writing. Below are examples of assignments that direct pupils to creative thinking.

Making up a creative text based on pictures (based on bringing different pictures into proportion). Various pictures are given, and it is necessary to make up a text (story, fairy tale, poem, song, narration...) by connecting them.

The method "Fifth (sixth, seventh...) is extra".

This method is of particular importance in pupils' acquisition of logical thinking skills. When using it, the following actions are performed:

- formation of a system of concepts that serves to reveal the essence of the topic being studied;

- achieving the placement of four (five, six, ...) concepts related to the topic from the created system;

- assigning pupils the task of identifying a concept that is not related to the topic and removing it from the system;

- encouraging pupils to comment on the essence of their actions (in order to strengthen the topic, pupils should be required to comment on the concepts preserved in the system and justify the logical connection between them). Being able to show and justify the logical connection between the concepts that illuminate the essence of the topic forms in pupils the ability to think independently, to justify personal approaches, as well as to compare their personal opinions with the opinions of their peers.

For example: On the lessons on Native language and reading literacy, you can assign the task of finding the character not related to the story "Shippak".:

Grandmother, father, mother, father's brother, uncle's wife, Malika, Firdavs, grandfather, mother's brother.

Chainword - this method diagram consists of a page of questions and answers, the questions asked by the teacher are answered by the pupil. The teacher should only pay attention to the fact that the answer to question 2 should start with the same letter as the answer to question 1 ends with.

<u>Questions</u>	<u>Answers</u>
<u>The capital of Uzbekistan</u>	<u>Tashkent</u>
<u>A cunning animal</u>	<u>Fox</u>
<u>A reptile</u>	<u>Snake.....</u>

In conclusion, it can be said that every method focused on creative thinking is important because it directs children to creativity, inventing, discovering new things, and is aimed at forming life competencies.

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